

TEACH-NOLOGY: EXPLORING THE CHALLENGES OF MASTER TEACHERS ON ICT INTEGRATION TO INSTRUCTION

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TEACH-nology: Exploring the Challenges of Master Teachers on ICT Integration to Instruction

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Abstract

This qualitative research aimed to explore the challenges of master teachers on ICT integration to instruction which employed a multiple case study. Purposive sampling was utilized to identify the participants of this study, which included 6 public school teachers in Polomolok 2 District. The research determined that these master teachers faced a selection of difficulties, such as a lack of back computer technology knowledge, the difficulty of integrating digital technology in remote areas, fear and reliance on others for technological support, fear related to using technology, and time limits for learning new technologies. Also, the participants developed coping strategies including encouraging students' digital abilities, actively seeking out professional network support, and strategically integrating technology to improve the learning experience, the master teachers demonstrated resilience in the face of these difficulties. The research revealed significant findings about the advantages of technology in the classroom, such as enhanced instructional strategies, heightened student involvement, and the constant need for educators to advance their technical proficiency.

Keywords: *educational management, ICT, instruction, master teachers, multiple case study, Philippines*

Introduction

"Technology can become the 'wings' that will allow the educational world to fly farther and faster than ever before—if we allow it."
Jenny Arledge.

The proverb emphasizes how technology has great educational potential. Education can develop to an extent that has never been achieved before by integrating technology. It can provide access to vast knowledge and skills, increase engagement using technologies like virtual reality and online platforms, and give personalized learning experiences. Additionally, it promotes intercultural understanding, worldwide connections, and efficient evaluation and feedback. Technology adoption is crucial to upgrading education to new areas (Asad et al., 2021; Machado et al., 2018).

Moreover, technology has become an increasingly significant aspect of students' lives outside of school, and it may also help them understand complex issues or inspire peer cooperation within the classroom. Due to these improvements, modern educational practice recommends that master teachers integrate technology into their classrooms. It is impossible to overstate the value of the school's information and communication technology (ICT). ICT has the potential to be a powerful instrument for expanding educational possibilities. Technology can potentially increase access to education while improving its relevance and quality. Technology has introduced new difficulties to the quality of education. It has altered many parts of people's lives (Alkamel & Chouthaiwale, 2018; Kurt, 2018).

In addition, it was proposed that the purpose of this multiple case study was to investigate and comprehend the challenges and coping strategies that Master Teachers used while integrating ICT into their classroom instruction. This study asserts that knowing the master teachers' challenges and coping mechanisms could provide insights to the DepEd community, particularly the Poblacion Polomolok National High School teaching community, which is experiencing the same dilemma but has just keeping the struggles to themselves.

Literature Review

Information and communication technology (ICT) are now a part of everyday life in the twenty-first century. ICT refers to electronic devices (laptops and Chrome books), handheld devices (iPads and iPods), interactive devices (interactive whiteboards), application software, and social media tools. They are used for commerce, communication, information gathering, learning, and many other purposes. The 21st century's rapid globalization and digitization have changed how we connect, communicate, learn, and work. Even though many K–12 schools in the US have computers in the classrooms, some claim that little has changed in teaching methods or student results. It is frequently believed that simply having technology in the classroom would revolutionize how teachers provide teaching and improve student learning (Kiru, 2018; Pardede, 2020).

Also, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) supports or drives almost every human endeavor, including education. ICT is used in teaching, learning, assessment, course registration, and payment, among other things. ICT use in education leads to innovative, creative, and cognitive thinking, increasing production, efficiency, and educational outcomes. It also enhances the quality and quantity of education. Humans have endeavored to employ technology to help prolong their lives and enhance their standard of living, and education is no exception (Agrawal & Mittal, 2018; Nwosu et al., 2018).

Moreover, Master teachers face various problems, including a limited number of computers, a lack of time, technical help, and a lack of internet connection, to mention a few. It was also revealed that male teachers use video and radio more than female teachers. Elderly

instructors use video and radio in their teaching more than younger teachers—Master Teacher, teaching and learning between experienced and inexperienced instructors. The teacher training curriculum should be updated to allow for technology integration, and instructors and students should be given laptop computers to improve students' learning results. Additionally, teachers with more constructivist perceptions of mobile device teaching, such as facilitating students' understanding more conveniently or actively supporting student learning, appeared to achieve higher quality technology integration in their lesson plans than those with traditional perceptions. (Bariham, 2019; Tsai & Tsai, 2019).

God gave us technology as a gift. It may be the greatest gift that God has given us in the afterlife itself. It is the source of all arts, sciences, and civilizations. Because of technology, our world is today very different. It has altered the meaning of life and transformed many facets of it. No one can deny the profound influence of technology on all facets of life. Technology makes the automation of several manual tasks possible. Modern technology may also help with many challenging and significant tasks, making them more accessible and successful. Teachers' attitudes must be considered to profit fully from technology in education. These attitudes play a critical role in identifying and projecting future practical uses of technology in the classroom (Islahi, 2019; Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018).

Methodology

This research applied a descriptive qualitative method, particularly a case study. A case study is a research methodology used to produce a comprehensive, multifaceted understanding of a complex subject in a real-world setting. This design was judged appropriate because the current study investigates the difficulties master teachers have while integrating ICT into their lessons (Holleman et al., 2020; Rashid et al., 2019).

Purposive sampling was utilized to choose study participants. Purposive sampling, according to (Andrade, 2021; Campbell et al., 2020) is a sampling approach based on prior knowledge about a population and the objective of the study of the research in which I utilized personal judgment to determine the sample.

For theoretical saturation, six (6) middle or seasoned (ages 40 -59 years old) designated as master teachers from the Polomolok District 2 during the school year 2022-2023 were selected as participants. Furthermore, the participants described the beginning, middle, and end of their discussion regarding the difficulties in integrating ICT into instruction. Their initial questions centered on the challenge of integrating ICT into their lessons as master teachers. On the other hand, the middle question aimed to develop strategies or techniques to address these challenges when integrating ICT into instruction. Regarding the parallels and differences across the examples regarding problems, coping strategies, and insights, the last question addressed the grand tour question.

Selected were six (6) middle or seasoned (ages from 40-59 years old) designated as master teachers during the school year 2022-2023 as participants, I established inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria included being a master teacher within the age range of 40-59 years old, two (2) master teachers from the four (4) different schools in Polomolok District 2 during the school year 2022-2023. I also required that the participants have a minimum number of years, one (1) year in particular of experience as a master teacher, to ensure sufficient experience and knowledge to contribute to the study.

Results and Discussion

Lack of Background Knowledge in ICT

MTP1- Virgo has taught Grade 9 students at Araling Panlipunan for the past four years as a master teacher. Despite her active and committed teaching style, her early obstacles to using technology were evident. Motivated by schoolwork, she traversed the problematic field of ICT integration, struggling to understand computer programs and digging into the problematic coding field. Her challenges were made more complicated by her failure to remember complex code sequences and her lack of prior ICT experience. However, her permanent dedication to learning and improving her teaching techniques remained, showing that she was a brilliant and motivated teacher who believed in enhancing her career and her student's ability in the classroom.

Moreover, MTP2-Scorpio showed outstanding dedication in teaching high school students through grades 11 and 12 with an unyielding work ethic over her six years as a master teacher. However, ICT integration was a significant obstacle when it came time to use technology. Learning computer programs became an exhausting challenge as she struggled to remember complex sequences and cope with the technicalities of coding. Despite the significant challenges presented by integrating technology, she showed her loyalty to academic success by striving to comprehend ideas and achieve her goals, even in the face of sacrifice.

Dilemma on ICT Integration in Distant Areas

MTP4- Aries is known for his independent thinking and positive participation; pupils in the talented master teacher have taught grades 5 and 6 pupils for over 20 years. However, signal issues, connection failures, and extended blackouts presented significant challenges to integrating ICT equipment in distant places. These barriers hampered both class development and access to crucial technology resources. With the challenges, He still needs to change his commitment to developing engaging classrooms and the aim of finding solutions for the problems related to remote internet integration.

In addition, MTP5-Leo's work in rural areas shows the need for more technology to integrate ICT. His attempts to effectively incorporate ICT are limited by his poor access to the resources he needs, which is a significant obstacle. Due to the lack of technology in these remote places, there exist differences among students, which leads to an unequal engaging area. Even with his commitment, he finds it more challenging to overcome this obstacle, highlighting the critical need to close the technological barrier to promote fair learning opportunities in these far-flung places.

Furthermore, MTP6—Sagittarius is a teacher in a far-off place with few resources and no computer access, so integrating ICT has proven difficult. This weakness made it more challenging for ICT to be effectively integrated, which impacted students' learning in these areas and led to educational inequalities. The significant differences in technology use brought to light the unequal learning possibilities for children, and providing an inclusive and fair learning environment is essential.

Support Student to Excel in ICT Integration

MTP1- Virgo's approach to empowering students with ICT integration is to educate them about the technology, recognize their abilities, and stress its value in the classroom. She uses many forms of communication to enhance their education, and teaching students how to utilize technology well creates an environment favorable to success in the digital age. Additionally, MTP2-Scorpio ensures that equal ICT integration calls for action, such as providing computer access for practical experience and promoting PowerPoint use to advance technological know-how. Encouraging equal chances involves overcoming financial limitations, highlighting the role of ICT in education, and aiming for a welcoming classroom where all students can take advantage of technology.

Further, MTP3—Pisces uses ICT to improve students' abilities, which is fundamental for effective teaching. Students become more interested in learning and more motivated about ICT integration when she is involved in various ICT-related activities. This method ensures broad development and effective use of technology by increasing student involvement and attentiveness.

Moreover, MTP4-Aries encourages successful teaching by supporting group activities and sharing ICT tools. Peer learning improves the student's understanding by utilizing one another's knowledge and provides an engaging environment that encourages involvement with ICT. Through cooperative learning, students build their talents collaboratively and improve their ICT skills.

Furthermore, MTP6- Sagittarius uses ICT in their lessons to actively involve his students. Recognizing its use in the twenty-first century helps students get ready for the future. When he utilizes the foundation, this strategy aims to help students maintain their focus. ICT resources are maximized for effective instruction by exchanging techniques to avoid equipment damage.

Address the Challenge of ICT Positively

It is essential for successful education that MTP3- Pisces have a positive attitude when using ICT. While solving problems, helping others and asking for assistance positively overcome problems. Successful ICT integration and student engagement require acknowledging a certain amount of technical challenges, constantly improving abilities, and creating an enjoyable place to study. Meanwhile, MTP5-Leo's integration of ICT improves student involvement and requires backup in case of unexpected issues. For technology-based learning to be effective, fostering positive student reactions and promoting a balance between directed responses and individual problem-solving abilities is essential.

Also, MTP6-Sagittarius uses conventional visual aids and printed materials to provide continuing instruction despite technical problems. Despite the positive effects of technology, accepting difficulties positively acknowledges the possibility of interruptions. His capacity to overcome challenges demonstrates his determination in the face of technical limitations.

Advancements of ICT in Education

MTP1-Virgo's use of traditional visual aids ensures lessons even in the face of emerging difficulties, emphasizing the value of accepting difficulties despite technology's advantages. MTP1-Virgo's Despite current technological restrictions, the ability to persevere in these challenges highlights its resolve. Moreover, MTP2- Scorpio emphasizes the need to expand ICT access in school and its importance for educating students for their future careers. Giving equal chances and establishing a welcoming classroom for every student is a top priority for ICT integration. Additionally, using technology, primarily through ICT integration in the classroom, dramatically improves learning possibilities and results for MTP3-Pisces. This set of characteristics encourages innovative teaching strategies and customized learning, which also shows potential for future educational research and development developments.

Furthermore, the development made in ICT by MTP4- Aries is crucial in reducing educational inequities by providing fair access to educational materials, enabling learners to acquire skills more rapidly, and encouraging self-directed learning along with MTP6-Sagittarius's use of ICT in the classroom results in transformational experiences that raise student engagement and provide accessible improvements in learning outcomes, demonstrating the usefulness of the technology in supporting the learning process.

Fear and Reliance on Others

MTP1—Virgo feels uncomfortable using ICT because she worries about losing files and finds computer commands confusing. Due to her lack of confidence, students, family members, and even coworkers are asked for help, and she replies that she largely depends on other people to do ICT-related duties. Depending on outside assistance indicates a lack of confidence in one's ability and an overall

concern with ICT abilities.

Tends to Become Lazy

MTP1—Virgo says that in the age of digital technology, students are choosing shortcuts over traditional writing since typing is more accessible than handwriting. This development leads to the refusal to write by hand and the preference for digital copies and computer-based learning. However, in favor of rapid digital accessibility, this convenience-driven ability reduces active participation and lowers the depth of pen-to-paper communication.

Cause Students to be Tired

In today's education, as MTP2-Scorpio explains, students struggle with tiredness resulting from differences in the technology room: some like watching movies, while others find ICT boring and eventually fall asleep. This tiredness arises from a lack of interest and the consuming power of technology, which attracts students to games and other forms of entertainment. This fatigue gets classrooms, making it difficult for teachers to teach ICT in the face of this digital exhaustion.

Issue on Lack of Time in Learning ICT

Regarding studying and using ICT, MTP3-Pisces in education faces significant obstacles because of her demanding schedule and various tasks. Managing teaching obligations while gaining expertise in ICT can be challenging, and it takes time to resolve technical issues immediately. She wishes she had more time to make the most of ICT for her students. However, deadlines and limited internet access create a huge barrier that makes integrating technology into the classroom difficult.

Afraid of Being Left Behind in ICT Trend

MTP6-Sagittarius believes that keeping up with new technology is essential to be relevant in the quickly evolving teaching field. We cannot advance in the rapidly evolving ICT environment; we must constantly adapt. She finds herself in a challenging situation when effectively utilizing technology to preserve its transformative impact on her students' educational experiences since learning new ICT skills requires ongoing adaptation.

Learn from Difficulties in the Use of ICT

The challenges that MTP1-Virgo faces as she navigates the digital maze teach us unexpected things about troubleshooting and improving her ICT skills. Once these challenges are overcome, barriers provide opportunities for greater understanding. The ability to adjust, acquired via overcoming obstacles, is essential for accepting new technologies, translating technological issues into potential limitations, and turning each obstacle into a chance for development and expertise.

Get a Support System in Learning ICT

A robust support system is essential for learning ICT, and knowledgeable co-teachers may offer invaluable advice. As stated by MTP2-Scorpio, tutorials provide organized guidance toward ICT competency, acting as foundations of knowledge. In incorporating technology into education, younger, tech-savvy instructors inspire and contribute, demonstrating their skills and serving as sources of inspiration. Meanwhile, asking for assistance from peers, students, and desired ICT professionals becomes a collaborative strength.

Employ Collaborative Effort in Learning ICT

Collaboration promotes a wide range of common knowledge and collective progress in ICT integration, as described by MTP3-Pisces inclusive environments provide growth and support for her, regardless of their respective abilities. Coworkers exchanging ideas creates a network of shared knowledge and enhances social skills via collaboration. In contrast, peer mentoring creates a positive atmosphere for group learning and develops technology via collaborative contributions.

Integrate ICT in the Teaching Process

By improving class delivery through mobile devices and multimedia materials, MTP4-Aries on ICT integration has changed modern education by energizing students while enhancing elaboration. With its benefits, given the possibility of technology problems, it is essential to recognize the significance of a manual teaching method. This dual approach creates a solid foundation that guarantees ongoing information flow in education by integrating the strength of ICT with reliable traditional methods.

Maximizing Learning through ICT Integration

MTP5-Leo keeps up teaching while creating creative educational settings using a variety of teaching tactics that include ICT to enable enhanced lectures and discussions. By working together to emphasize additional learning materials and provide technological support, he and the students are empowered, increasing the resources available for deep understanding.

Educate Colleagues about ICT Integration

ICT integration is given priority in LAC sessions, which enable him to actively participate in technology-centered teaching by providing them with thorough training, as MTP6-Sagittarius emphasizes. The seminars, which explore online platforms for remote

communication and collaborative learning, focus on practical issues and provide specific instructions for effortless integration of ICT. This all-encompassing strategy encourages a culture of lifelong learning and gives him adaptable resources to succeed in the new digital learning environment.

Evolution of Teaching Methods

MTP1-Virgo highlights how ICT's progressive change is transforming education by changing methods of instruction and emphasizing its crucial role in creating the future of teaching. ICT proficiency not only improves teaching strategies but also gives educators the ability to manage the changing face of education skillfully. Future ICT changes, such as immersive experiences and adjustable systems, highlight the need for educators to continuously improve their abilities to provide an environment filled with learning and prepared for new challenges.

Application of ICT Learning

Integration of ICT in education involves more than simply skill acquisition; it necessitates active application in instructional approaches. For successful learning, MTP2-Scorpio stresses that knowledge in ICT needs to move from academic to actual implementation, supporting a hands-on approach for students and interacting with peers. The determination to create and design an engaging educational experience for her students is essential in transformational ICT learning.

Promote Class Interaction when Teaching ICT

MTP3-Pisces shows that active student involvement reigns supreme in ICT integration as educators seek to inspire passion and develop changing learning environments. Her journey is more than just information transmission; it is about establishing a varied, enjoyable educational environment. Beyond the classroom, ICT is essential for breaking down barriers and ensuring equal access to excellent education for all students, regardless of background or location. This technology-driven accessibility promotes education as an evident responsibility for her.

Facilitation of Learning Becomes Easy

Enhancing teaching experiences is made possible by the accessibility of many educational resources. MTP4—Aries' knowledge of the simple integration of ICT helps him navigate many resources necessary for his teaching requirements. Beyond accessibility, ICT significantly affects learning and skill development as MTP4—Aries leads pupils to absorb, retain, and apply material effectively using these new tools.

Enhance Knowledge about the Use of ICT

MTP5-Leo demonstrates that competency in ICT technologies is essential for effectively integrating traditional and varied materials into classroom education. His journey tries to integrate ICT technology with traditional methods, changing educational techniques to revive and improve the learning experience.

Emphasize the Need for Upgrading ICT Skills

MTP6-Sagittarius keeps enhancing his ICT skills in today's changing educational world. He is learning about numerous ICT platforms. As technology transforms modern education, he is already actively involved in developing his skills through training and seminars to create active learning environments.

Fear and Reliance on Others

MTP1- Virgo feels uncomfortable using ICT because she worries about losing files and finds computer commands confusing. Due to her lack of confidence, students, family members, and even coworkers are asked for help, and she relies mainly on other people to do ICT-related duties. Depending on outside assistance indicates a lack of confidence in one's ability and an overall concern with ICT abilities.

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MTP6-Sagittarius believes that keeping up with new technology is essential to be relevant in the quickly evolving teaching field. We cannot advance still in the rapidly evolving ICT environment; we must constantly adapt. She finds herself in a challenging situation when effectively utilizing technology to preserve its transformative impact on her students' educational experiences since learning new ICT skills requires ongoing adaptation.

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Evolution of Teaching Methods

MTP1-Virgo highlights how ICT's progressive chance is transforming education by changing methods of instruction and emphasizing its crucial role in creating the future of teaching. ICT proficiency improves teaching strategies and allows educators to manage the changing face of education skillfully. Future ICT changes, such as immersive experiences and adjustable systems, highlight the need for educators to continuously improve their abilities to provide an environment filled with learning and prepared for new challenges.

Application of ICT Learning

Integration of ICT in education involves more than simply skill acquisition; it necessitates active application in instructional approaches. For successful learning, MTP2-Scorpio stresses that knowledge in ICT needs to move from academic to actual

implementation, supporting a hands-on approach for students and interacting with peers. The determination to create and design an engaging educational experience for her students is essential in transformational ICT learning.

Promote Class Interaction when Teaching ICT

MTP3-Pisces shows that active student involvement reigns supreme in ICT integration as educators seek to inspire passion and develop changing learning environments. Her journey is more than just information transmission; it is about establishing a varied, enjoyable educational environment. Beyond the classroom, ICT is essential for breaking down barriers and ensuring equal access to excellent education for all students, regardless of background or location. This technology-driven accessibility promotes education as an evident responsibility for her.

Facilitation of Learning Becomes Easy

The accessibility of a wide range of educational materials improves teaching experiences. MTP4- Aries's knowledge of simple ICT integration helps him navigate many resources necessary for his teaching requirements. Beyond accessibility, ICT significantly affects learning and skill development as MTP4- Aries leads pupils to absorb, retain, and apply material effectively using these new tools.

Enhance Knowledge about the Use of ICT

MTP-Leo displays that competency in ICT technologies is essential for effectively integrating traditional and varied materials into classroom education. His journey tries to integrate ICT technology with traditional methods, changing educational techniques to revive and improve the learning experience.

Emphasize the Need for Upgrading ICT Skills

MTP6-Sagittarius keeps enhancing his ICT skills in today's changing educational world. He is learning about numerous ICT platforms. As technology transforms modern education, he is already actively involved in developing his skills through training and seminars to create active learning environments.

Fear and Reliance on Others

MTP1- Virgo feels uncomfortable while using ICT because she worries about losing files and finds computer commands confusing. Due to her lack of confidence, students, family members, and even coworkers are asked for help, and she`'s rely largely on other people to do ICT-related duties. Depending on outside assistance is indicative of a lack of confidence in one's own ability and an overall concern with ICT abilities.

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Issue on Lack of Time in Learning ICT

When it comes to studying and using ICT, MTP3-Pisces in the education area faces significant obstacles because of her hard schedule and variety of tasks. Managing teaching obligations while gaining expertise in ICT can be challenging, and it takes time to resolve technical issues immediately. She wishes she had more time to make the most of ICT for her students, but deadlines and limited internet access create a huge barrier that makes integrating technology into the classroom difficult.

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Promote Class Interaction when Teaching ICT

MTP3-Pisces shows that in the field of ICT integration, active student involvement reigns supreme as educators seek to inspire passion and develop changing learning environments. her journey is about more than just information transmission; it's about establishing a varied, enjoyable educational environment. Beyond the classroom, ICT serves as an important tool for breaking down barriers and ensuring equal access to excellent education for all students, regardless of background or location. This technology-driven accessibility promotes education as an evident responsibility on her.

Facilitation of Learning Becomes Easy

The accessibility of a wide range of educational materials in education improves teaching experiences. MTP4- Aries knowledge of Simple integration of ICT helps him to navigate lots of resources made to his teaching requirements. Beyond accessibility, ICT has a major effect on learning and skill development as MTP4- Aries lead pupils to absorb, retain, and apply material effectively using these

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MTP-Leo displays that competency in ICT technologies is essential for the effective integration traditional and varied materials into classroom education. His journey tries to integrate ICT technology with traditional methods, changing educational techniques in order to revive and improve the learning experience.

Emphasize the Need for Upgrading ICT Skills

MTP6-Sagittarius keeps enhancing his ICT skills in today's changing educational world. He is learning about numerous ICT platforms. As technology transforms modern education, he is already actively involved in developing his skills through training and seminars to create active learning environments.

Table 1. Cross-case analysis of the challenges, coping mechanisms and insights of Master Teachers when integrating ICT into their instruction

Category	Emergent Themes	Indication/Case		Remarks
		Similarities	Differences	
Challenges	Lack of Background Knowledge in ICT	Virgo and Scorpio		Virgo and Scorpio have the same challenges Cases of Aries and Leo have common challenges
	Dilemma on ICT Integration in Distant Areas	Aries and Leo		
	Learn from Difficulties on the use of ICT		Virgo	Only Virgo has difficulty on the use of ICT
Coping Mechanisms	Support Student to Excel in ICT Integration	Virgo, Pisces, Aries, and Sagittarius		Virgo, Pisces, Aries, and Sagittarius cope through Support Student to Excel in ICT Integration
	Address the Challenges of ICT Positively	Leo and Sagittarius	Virgo, Pisces, Aries and Sagittarius	Virgo, Pisces, Aries and Sagittarius Cope though support System in Learning ICT
	Get support System in Learning ICT			Only Pisces cope through Employ Colloaborative Effort in Learning ICT
	Employ Colloaborative Effort in Learning ICT		Pisces	Only Aries cope through Integrate ICT in the Teaching Process
	Integrate ICT in the Teaching Process		Aries	Only Leo cope through Maximaxing Learning through ICT Integration
	Maximaxing Learning through ICT Integration		Leo	Only Aries cope through Educate Collegues about ICT Integration
	Educate Collegues about ICT Integration		Aries	Virgo and Aries have an insight in Advancement of ICT
Insights	Advancement of ICT in Education	Virgo and Aries		Virgo and Aries have an insight in Advancement of ICT
	Emphasize the Need for Upgrading ICT Skills	Leo		Only Leo has an insight of Emphasize the Need for Upgrading ICT Skills
	Evolution of Teaching Methods	Sagittarius		Only Sagittarius has an insight in ICT Skills Evolution of Teaching
	Application of ICT Learning		Virgo	Only Virgo has an insight in Application of ICT Learning
	Promotes Class Interaction when Teaching ICT		Virgo	Only Virgo has an insight in Promotes Interaction Teaching ICT
	Facilitation of Learning Becomes Easy		Pisces	Only Pisces Learning Becomes Easy
	Enchance the Use of ICT		Leo	Only Leo has an insight of Enchance the Use of ICT

Studies revealed based on their personal challenges, seven emergent themes were formulated, and these were: Lack of background knowledge in ICT, Dilemma on ICT Integration in Distant Areas, Fear and Reliance on Others, Tends to Become Lazy, Cause Students to be Tired, Issue on Lack of Time in Learning ICT and Afraid of Being Left Behind in ICT Trend. Also, Based on their coping mechanisms, eight emergent themes were formulated, and these were: Support Student to Excel in ICT Integration, Address the Challenge of ICT Positively, Learn from Difficulties on the Use of ICT, Get a Support System in Learning ICT, Employ Collaborative Effort in Learning ICT, Integrate ICT in the Teaching Process, Maximizing Learning through ICT Integration, and Educate Colleagues about ICT Integration and Based on the insights of master teacher in ICT integration to instruction, seven emergent themes were formulated, and these were: Advancements of ICT in Education, Evolution of Teaching Methods, Application of ICT Learning, Promote Class Interaction when Teaching ICT, Facilitation of Learning Becomes Easy, Enhance Knowledge about the Use of ICT, and Emphasize the Need for Upgrading ICT Skills.

Conclusions

Master teachers are trailblazers in education and significantly influence how students learn. Their ability to successfully integrate ICT improves education overall and equips students for success in a fast-changing digital world. Master educators use technology to build engaging, student-centered learning environments that promote digital literacy, collaboration, and critical thinking. Additionally, by incorporating ICT, these teachers can modify their lessons to fit the unique learning preferences of each student, making learning exciting and individualized. Master teachers foster a culture of continuous growth by being lifelong learners and motivating their peers to adopt cutting-edge teaching techniques and increase their ICT proficiency. In a nutshell, master teachers' dedication to using ICT revolutionizes classrooms today and stimulates the growth of future-ready, flexible, and technologically competent individuals.

Master teachers are innovators in the field, driving transformation and utilizing ICT to its total capacity to pursue academic success. In an educational setting where students are more than just consumers of knowledge but actively engaged in their learning process, their dedication to lifelong learning, flexibility, and creative pedagogy foster excellence. Master teachers who incorporate ICT into their instruction have a significant impact outside of the classroom, shaping the larger educational community and advancing the development of instructional strategies. The role that master teachers play in ensuring that students are not only knowledgeable but also have the skills necessary to succeed in a dynamic, digitally connected environment is becoming increasingly crucial as technology continues to change the educational landscape.

In conclusion, a Master teacher's position is crucial in integrating ICT and time management into courses. A key component of good teaching in the digital age is their skill in utilizing specific ICT programs. Gaining knowledge through training, seminars, and workshops is essential to overcoming challenges. These platforms offer strategies and the instruments needed to conquer challenges and guarantee the effortless integration of technology into education. The commitment to lifelong learning and flexibility when utilizing these tools well, in the end, enable schools to maximize their instructional strategies and prepare students for success in a society that is becoming more and more tech-driven.

Public elementary and high school Master teachers have various challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights on ICT integration into instructions. Here are some implications for practice:

Lack of Background Knowledge in ICT. School administrators must provide specialized training sessions, seminars, or workshops to improve ICT skills. These courses must start with basics and work up to more challenging topics, ensuring educators can successfully use technology in their teaching.

Dilemma on ICT Integration in Distant Areas. School heads must plan and implement flexible learning approaches that take advantage of various schedules and situations. This could include blended learning strategies, in which some instruction is delivered online in addition to printed materials or face-to-face discussions.

Support Student to Excel in ICT Integration. School heads must use project-based methods of instruction that require students to use ICT technologies to complete practical tasks. Students may work on projects or difficulties from the real world while improving their abilities with this practical application.

Address the Challenge of ICT Positively. School leaders must demonstrate the efficient utilization of ICT in their procedures, showing how valuable it is and motivating educators to follow their example. Leaders who value technology set the standard for its use in education.

Advancements of ICT in Education. The Department of Education has established an environment that encourages creativity and the experimentation of new technologies. Encourage Master Teachers to learn and experiment with new topics continuously.

Fear and Reliance on Others. School leaders need to encourage a culture that accepts failure. Master teachers should be urged to see difficulties as development opportunities rather than failures. Emphasize that asking for assistance and making errors are acceptable.

Tends to Become Lazy. School Administrators need to develop classes that utilize engaging and interactive ICT resources. To make learning more engaging for students, use multimedia, gaming, and collaboration platforms.

Cause Students to be Tired. School administrators must provide students with different options so they may select the resources or platforms that work best for them. To boost engagement, take seriously their interests while developing the learning process.

Issue on Lack of Time in Learning ICT. Organize ICT instruction into manageable, small portions for simple understanding by School Heads. Help Master Teachers better integrate learning into their timetables by offering short, specialized programs that may be finished in a shorter period.

Afraid of Being Left Behind in ICT Trend. School leaders need to provide one-on-one assistance through mentorship or coaching activities. Assign mentors or tech-savvy coworkers who can offer personalized guidance according to the particular needs and learning style of each Master Teacher.

Learn from Difficulties on the Use of ICT. It is recommended that school supervisors support Master teachers in periodically reflecting

on their experiences integrating ICT. Promote self-evaluation by noting what went well, what did not, and why. This self-examination assists in problem understanding and solution identification.

Get a Support System in Learning ICT. When Master teachers need help addressing technology difficulties, school administrators should have resources or specialized technical support staff they may contact immediately.

Employ Collaborative Effort in Learning ICT. School officials must use virtual collaboration tools that enable Master Teachers to exchange materials, pose queries, and work together digitally. Social media groups, forums, and shared documents can facilitate continuous cooperation.

Integrate ICT in the Teaching Process. Education leaders need to get connected to discuss how to incorporate ICT into classes gradually, starting with small actions. Introduce new progressively advanced technologies as teachers and students get used to them, starting with standard devices or fundamental applications.

They are maximizing Learning through ICT Integration. Explore the flipped classroom strategy, which changes the order of typical teaching techniques. Through shows or online resources, students acquire material outside of the classroom, free up class time for application, discussion, and teamwork.

Educate Colleagues about ICT Integration—present practical instances of integrating ICT in your classroom. Provide examples of how technology may improve your teaching strategies and student engagement, or ask colleagues to watch.

Evolution of Teaching Methods. Remain informed about the most recent advancements, trends, and ICT tools in education. Attend workshops, conferences, and online courses to keep up with the latest developments in education.

Application of ICT Learning. The head of the school must make sure that all technology use directly supports and corresponds with the curriculum's learning objectives. Choose ICT resources or techniques that support the learning objectives.

Promote Class Interaction when Teaching ICT. The school's principal must be sure that it integrates interactive tools that promote student cooperation in real time. Tools like Microsoft Teams, Google Workspace, and collaborative whiteboards make simultaneous participation and engagement possible.

Facilitation of Learning Becomes Easy. The school director is obligated to ensure that educational technology is introduced in a way that is easy for Master Teachers and students to utilize. Give preference to tools with user-friendly interfaces and offer tutorials or step-by-step instructions.

Enhance Knowledge about the Use of ICT. The school supervisor must be sure to promote reading blogs, journals, and publications about educational technology, including the latest ICT applications in the classroom. Teachers keep up to date on the newest trends by subscribing to periodicals or websites that are relevant to them.

Emphasize the Need for Upgrading ICT Skills. The educational officer of the school must be sure to plan seminars emphasizing the practical application of ICT technologies in the classroom and hands-on learning. Allow Master Teachers to try new things and apply their knowledge to classroom situations.

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